

1 **Imaging xCT with immunoPET in therapy-resistant non-small cell lung cancer**

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1 **Abstract**

2 Therapy resistance presents a major clinical challenge in non-small cell lung cancer (NSCLC),
3 contributing to its high mortality rate. Overexpression of the amino acid transporter xCT frequently
4 mediates treatment resistance in NSCLC and can be therapeutically targeted with antibody-drug
5 conjugates. Here, we developed a corresponding immunoPET radiotracer to non-invasively
6 evaluate xCT expression in NSCLC and visualize pharmacokinetics of xCT-targeting antibodies.

7 **Methods:** Specificity of xCT-targeting antibodies, HM30 and HM34, was assessed by western
8 blotting, immunocytochemistry, and internalization studies. Next, HM30/34 were conjugated to
9 deferoxamine (DFO) via their lysine residues and radiolabeled with zirconium-89.
10 Immunoreactivity was determined by bead- and cell-based binding assays. Preclinical *in vivo*
11 pharmacokinetics of the ⁸⁹Zr-labeled antibodies were evaluated through longitudinal imaging
12 studies and *ex vivo* biodistribution using subcutaneous and orthotopic models of NSCLC.

13 **Results:** Through multiple biochemical methods, we demonstrate excellent target specificity and
14 rapid antibody internalization. ImmunoPET agents [⁸⁹Zr]Zr-DFO-HM30 and [⁸⁹Zr]Zr-DFO-HM34
15 were produced with good yield and radiochemical purity with no impact on immunoreactivity. Both
16 agents clearly delineated xCT-high H460 tumors *in vivo*. Conversely, [⁸⁹Zr]Zr-DFO-HM30 binding
17 was low in low xCT-expressing H1299 tumors. [⁸⁹Zr]Zr-DFO-HM30 imaging and autoradiography
18 of H460 orthotopic lung tumors revealed lesion-specific binding.

19 **Conclusion:** Our findings provide robust evidence for the use of immunoPET as a research tool
20 to image elevated xCT expression and visualize tumor penetration of xCT-directed antibodies.
21 This tool can inform the development of enhanced antibody-based therapeutic candidates against
22 treatment-resistant phenotypes to ultimately improve survival outcomes in NSCLC.

23

24 **Key words:** xCT; immunoPET; therapy resistance; non-small cell lung cancer; molecular
25 imaging

1 **Graphical Abstract:**

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1 Introduction

2 Outcomes for patients with non-small cell lung cancer (NSCLC) remain poor, with a 10-year
3 survival rate of 11% (1). Patients are frequently diagnosed with late-stage disease, and resistance
4 to standard-of-care therapy commonly arises. Antioxidant systems are essential for cancer cell
5 adaptability, influencing tumor initiation, progression, and treatment resistance (2,3). Importantly,
6 elevated antioxidant capacity enables tumors to withstand heightened oxidative stress arising
7 from intrinsic metabolic activity and external therapeutic insult (4,5). Glutathione (GSH), a major
8 intracellular antioxidant, is vital to maintain redox balance in NSCLC (6). GSH biosynthesis is
9 increased in NSCLC by activating mutations in the transcription factor nuclear factor erythroid 2-
10 related factor 2 (NRF2) or its negative regulator, kelch-like ECH-associated protein 1 (KEAP1),
11 which occurs in approximately one-third of NSCLC patients (7). NRF2 activation directly drives
12 GSH synthesis through both the upregulation of biosynthetic enzymes and increased uptake of
13 amino acids from the tumor microenvironment (8). One of these amino acids, cystine, is rate-
14 limiting for GSH production (9) and is supplied largely via the cystine/glutamate antiporter, xCT
15 (SLC7A11). As xCT is under the transcriptional control of NRF2, targeting xCT offers a promising
16 avenue to image the antioxidant capacity of tumors and treat resistant disease.

17 Despite the compelling role of xCT in cancer cell survival and therapy resistance, it has been
18 underutilized as a therapeutic target to-date. Past efforts have focused on FDA-approved small-
19 molecule xCT inhibitor sulfasalazine and its synergistic effect with platinum-based
20 chemotherapies (10-12). Unfortunately, combination trials in humans have proved unsuccessful,
21 largely due to low systemic bioavailability and insufficient specificity (13,14). To overcome these
22 limitations, we have previously investigated the targeted delivery of a cytotoxic payload to tumor
23 cells using HM30-Tesirine, an xCT-targeting antibody-drug conjugate (ADC). HM30-Tesirine
24 demonstrated robust tumor growth inhibition and improved survival in a preclinical model of
25 therapy-resistant NSCLC (15), highlighting the promise of antibody-based approaches targeting
26 elevated xCT expression.

27 To fully realize the therapeutic potential of xCT-targeted biologics, a more rigorous understanding
28 of antibody–target engagement and systemic pharmacokinetics is required. Positron emission
29 tomography (PET) imaging offers a powerful, non-invasive approach to quantify target expression
30 and engagement with high sensitivity. Several small-molecule PET radiotracers, such as
31 [¹⁸F]FSPG, [¹⁸F]FRPG, [¹⁸F]hGST13, and [¹⁸F]FASu, have been developed to visualize xCT
32 function *in vivo* (16-19). Whilst providing valuable insights into treatment response and target
33 expression (20-22), these small-molecule tracers cannot capture the target-binding properties

1 and pharmacokinetics of antibody-based therapeutics against xCT. To address this limitation, we
2 developed and tested [⁸⁹Zr]Zr-DFO-HM30 and [⁸⁹Zr]Zr-DFO-HM34 as immunoPET companion
3 diagnostics.

4

5 **Methods**

6 Additional methods are described in the supplemental information.

7

8 Conjugation and radiolabeling

9 Lysine residues on HM30, HM34, and control human IgG1 (BioXcell) were labeled using *p*-SCN-
10 Bn-Deferoxamine (DFO; B-705, Macrocyclics). A previously published two-step method,
11 consisting of chelator-antibody conjugation and subsequent radiolabeling, was used
12 (**Supplemental Fig. 1**) (23). Briefly, a five-fold molar excess of *p*-SCN-Bn-DFO in 20 μL DMSO
13 (4-7 mM, 3-5 mg/mL) was added to 2-4 mg antibody (1 mL) and incubated for 1 h (37°C, 550
14 rpm). The reaction product was then purified using a PD-10 column (Cytiva), eluting with PBS (2
15 mL).

16 For radiolabeling, zirconium-89 in 1 M oxalic acid (Revvity) was neutralized with 2 M sodium
17 carbonate before incubation with DFO-conjugated antibodies (DFO-Abs) in 0.5 M HEPES buffer
18 for 1 h at room temperature (RT, 550 rpm). For *in vitro* productions, 4-8 MBq zirconium-89 was
19 added to 20 μg of DFO-Ab. For *in vivo* productions, 40-80 MBq zirconium-89 was added to 200-
20 500 μg of DFO-Ab. [⁸⁹Zr]Zr-DFO-Abs were purified using a PD-10 column and eluted with PBS (2
21 mL) in four 500 μL fractions. Radiochemical conversion and radiochemical purity were assessed
22 as detailed in the supplemental information. Radiolabeling yields have not been decay-corrected.

23

24 Bead-based immunoreactivity

25 The immunoreactivity of [⁸⁹Zr]Zr-DFO-HM30/34 was measured by a bead-based assay, as
26 described by Sharma *et al.* (24). Briefly, 20 μL DynaBeads™ MyOne™ Streptavidin-T1
27 (Invitrogen) were washed by adding 380 μL PBS with 0.05% Tween20 (PBS-T), followed by brief
28 vortexing. Beads were isolated using the DynaMag™ magnetic rack (Invitrogen) before incubation
29 with 2 μg of biotinylated xCT antigen (amino acid sequence: KGQTQNFKDAFSGRDSSITRLP)
30 for 15 min with end-to-end rotation. Following antigen loading, the beads were washed three

1 times. Next, 1 ng of [⁸⁹Zr]Zr-DFO-HM30/34 (~250 Bq), with and without 5 µg of unlabeled
2 antibody, were added to the beads and incubated for 30 min (RT with rotation). The beads were
3 isolated, and the supernatant was collected in fresh Eppendorf tubes. The beads were then
4 washed twice with PBS-T, with the washes also collected in fresh Eppendorf tubes. Finally,
5 radioactivity in the supernatant, washes and beads were measured in a LKB Wallac 1282
6 CompuGamma (PerkinElmer). The immunoreactivity was calculated using the following equation,
7 where CPM denotes counts per minute:

$$8 \quad \text{Immunoreactivity (\% total activity)} = \left(\frac{\text{bead CPM}}{\text{supernatant CPM} + \text{washes CPM} + \text{bead CPM}} \right) * 100$$

9

10 Animal studies

11 All animal experiments were performed in accordance with the United Kingdom Home Office
12 Animal (scientific procedures) Act 1986 under project license PP9982297 and received local
13 Animal Welfare and Ethical Review Body approval.

14

15 Longitudinal PET/CT imaging

16 Mice were anaesthetized (1-2% isoflurane in O₂) before intravenous injection through a tail vein
17 cannula of 10 µg [⁸⁹Zr]Zr-DFO-Ab (~2 MBq) with and without 90 µg of unlabeled Ab, in 100 µL
18 PBS. Static PET imaging scans were acquired at 4, 24, 48, 72, 96 or 144 h post-injection (p.i.) on
19 a Mediso NanoScan PET/CT system (1-5 coincidence mode, 3D reconstruction with CT-based
20 attenuation and scatter corrections) using a 4-bed mouse hotel (25). Scan time was increased at
21 each time point to account for the half-life of zirconium-89 (3.3 d), ranging from 30 to 90 min. CT
22 images were acquired for anatomical visualization and attenuation correction (720 projections,
23 helical acquisition, 50 kV, 300 ms exposure). Static PET image reconstruction was performed
24 using the 3D Tera-Tomo algorithm (4 iterations, 6 subsets, 0.4 mm isotropic voxel size, 400-600
25 keV energy window). InterviewFusion software (v3.11.011, Mediso) was used for automatic 4-
26 bed hotel separation. The DICOMs for individual mice were imported into VivoQuant software
27 (v5.4.2, Perceptive) for image quantification. Tissue volumes of interest were compiled from
28 manually drawn sequential 2D regions of interest from the CT images. The radioactivity in each
29 tissue was expressed as a percentage of the injected dose per gram of tissue volume (% ID/g).

30

1 Ex vivo biodistribution

2 Following completion of the final PET/CT imaging scans, mice were sacrificed, and tissues of
3 interest were harvested and weighed. The radioactivity in each tissue was measured using a LKB
4 Wallac 1282 CompuGamma (PerkinElmer). To allow accurate quantification of the radioactivity,
5 serially diluted zirconium-89 standards were measured in parallel. Radioactivity measurements
6 were decay-corrected to the time of injection and normalized to tissue weight.

7

8 Statistical analysis

9 Data were expressed as mean \pm SD. Significance was determined by ordinary one-way ANOVA
10 with Dunnett's or Tukey's post-hoc test, two-way ANOVA with Bonferroni correction for multiple
11 comparisons or Welch's t-test (v10.3.1, GraphPad Software). Differences between groups were
12 considered significant if $P < 0.05$.

13

14

15 **Results**

16 Monoclonal antibodies HM30 and HM34 selectively bind to xCT

17 The monoclonal antibodies used in this study, HM30 and HM34, were provided by AgilVax (patent
18 WO2020/227640A1). Both are humanized IgG1 antibodies that target human xCT at an epitope
19 within its extracellular domain 3 (**Fig. 1A**). To confirm target specificity, a panel of human NSCLC
20 cell lines with varying xCT expression were probed by western blot using these antibodies. HM30
21 and HM34 differentiated between high- and low-xCT expressing cells, with the magnitude of xCT
22 expression matching data generated using a commercially available antibody (**Fig. 1B**;
23 **Supplemental Fig. 2**). Surface plasmon resonance also confirmed the high affinity of antibodies
24 for their target antigen ($K_D = 0.08$ nM and 0.11 nM for HM30 and HM34, respectively,
25 **Supplemental Fig. 3**). Cell-membrane binding of HM30 and HM34 was confirmed by confocal
26 microscopy in xCT-high H460 cells, with staining co-localized with membrane-specific CellBrite®
27 fluorescence (**Fig. 1C**). Further, HM30 and HM34 mAbs were rapidly internalized by H460 cells,
28 with pHrodoRed fluorescence of labeled mAbs increasing in a time-dependent manner following
29 the activation of fluorescence in the acidic environment of endosomes and lysosomes (**Fig. 1D**).

30

1
 2 **Figure 1. Specificity of HM30 and HM34 for xCT.** **A.** Protein structure of xCT (blue) and its associated CD98 heavy
 3 chain (CD98hc, grey), required for membrane localization (PDB ID: 7EPZ) (26). The antibody target sequence is
 4 highlighted in red. **B.** xCT expression determined by western blot using HM30 and HM34 as primary antibodies,
 5 alongside a commercial antibody, Cell Signaling Technology (CST) #12691. Actin was used as a loading control. **C.**
 6 Immunocytochemistry with H460 cells, visualizing membrane localization of HM30 and HM34 staining. **D.** Flow
 7 cytometric assessment of pHrodoRed-labeled HM30 and HM34 internalization in H460 cells over a 4 h time course (n
 8 = 3). Comparisons to 0 min timepoint were made by one-way ANOVA with Dunnett's post hoc test.

9

10 Radiolabeling of HM30 and HM34 does not affect immunoreactivity

11 Mass spectrometry revealed a chelate-to-antibody ratio of 1.84 for DFO-HM30 and 1.72 for DFO-
 12 HM34. Importantly, DFO-conjugation to HM30/34 had no impact on xCT binding, as shown by
 13 flow cytometry and immunoprecipitation assays (**Fig. 2A, Supplemental Fig. 4**). Subsequent
 14 radiolabeling produced [⁸⁹Zr]Zr-DFO-HM30 and [⁸⁹Zr]Zr-DFO-HM34 in yields of 82.5 ± 12.4% (n
 15 = 4) and 94.8 ± 5.4% (n = 5), respectively with high radiochemical purity (RCP; 98.1 ± 1.6% for
 16 [⁸⁹Zr]Zr-DFO-HM30, n = 4; and 97.3 ± 1.0% for [⁸⁹Zr]Zr-DFO-HM34, n = 5). RCP was confirmed
 17 by fast-protein liquid chromatography and subsequent gamma counting, with antibody integrity
 18 confirmed via SDS-PAGE with phosphoimaging (**Supplemental Fig. 5**). The specific activity of

1 the radioimmunoconjugates was 0.225 ± 0.090 MBq/ μ g ($n = 4$) and 0.268 ± 0.089 MBq/ μ g ($n = 5$)
 2 for [89 Zr]Zr-DFO-HM30 and [89 Zr]Zr-DFO-HM34, respectively.

3 Post-radiolabeling, a bead-based antigen-binding assay was performed to determine antibody
 4 immunoreactivity. Both [89 Zr]Zr-DFO-HM30 and [89 Zr]Zr-DFO-HM34 had high immunoreactivity to
 5 the target antigen (86.4% and 86.1%, respectively, $P < 0.0001$ compared to unloaded control
 6 beads; **Fig. 2B**). Notably, the binding of the radiolabeled mAbs to the target antigen was blocked
 7 by >70% when co-incubated with a 5000-fold excess of the corresponding unlabeled mAb (P
 8 < 0.0001 , $n = 3$; **Fig. 2B**), further indicating specificity for xCT. Finally, [89 Zr]Zr-DFO-HM30 was
 9 evaluated in H1299 and H1975 NSCLC cells, which exhibit low basal xCT expression. Treatment
 10 of these cells with ki696, a NRF2 pathway activator (15), increased xCT expression and [89 Zr]Zr-
 11 DFO-HM30 cell binding by 2.4-fold compared with untreated controls ($P = 0.0016$ and $P = 0.0005$
 12 for H1299 and H1975 cells, respectively; **Fig. 2C**).

13

14

15 **Figure 2. Immunoreactivity of DFO-HM30/34 and [89 Zr]Zr-DFO-HM30/34.** **A.** (Top) Flow cytometric analysis of
 16 unconjugated vs DFO-conjugated HM30/34 binding to H460 cells ($n = 3$). The median fluorescence intensity (MFI) of
 17 each mAb was normalized to the average MFI of their respective unconjugated mAbs to yield relative cell binding
 18 values. (Bottom) Western blot following immunoprecipitation of xCT from H460 lysate, comparing unconjugated and
 19 DFO-conjugated antibodies. Detection was performed with a commercial antibody. **B.** Bead-based immunoreactivity
 20 assay of 89 Zr-labeled antibodies with immobilized target peptide ± 5000 -fold excess of the corresponding unlabeled
 21 mAb ($n = 3$). Unloaded beads were included as a control. **C.** (Top) Cell-binding of [89 Zr]Zr-DFO-HM30 in NSCLC cell
 22 lines pre- and post-treatment with 200 μ m ki696. (Bottom) xCT expression post-ki696 treatment. Actin was included as
 23 a loading control. For A-C, comparisons were made by one-way ANOVA with Tukey's post hoc test.

1 [⁸⁹Zr]Zr-DFO-HM30 and [⁸⁹Zr]Zr-DFO-HM34 bind to NSCLC tumors *in vivo*

2 To evaluate the ability of [⁸⁹Zr]Zr-DFO-HM30 and [⁸⁹Zr]Zr-DFO-HM34 to identify xCT-expressing
3 NSCLC tumors, longitudinal PET/CT imaging was performed in female mice bearing
4 subcutaneous H460 tumors. At 4 h p.i., both [⁸⁹Zr]Zr-DFO-HM30 and [⁸⁹Zr]Zr-DFO-HM34
5 remained in circulation, illustrated by high levels of radioactivity in the heart, carotid arteries and
6 descending aorta (**Fig. 3A, Supplemental Fig. 6**). Tumor accumulation of both agents was
7 present at 24 h p.i. and there were no differences in tumor binding between [⁸⁹Zr]Zr-DFO-HM30
8 and [⁸⁹Zr]Zr-DFO-HM34 at any of the timepoints tested ($P > 0.05$, $n = 4$; **Fig. 3B**). *Ex vivo*
9 biodistribution studies confirmed tumor binding of both agents at 96 h p.i. ($10.34 \pm 0.60\%$ ID/g for
10 [⁸⁹Zr]Zr-DFO-HM30 and $7.54 \pm 1.23\%$ ID/g with [⁸⁹Zr]Zr-DFO-HM34; **Fig 3C**). Off-target
11 accumulation was observed in the liver, spleen, and knee and shoulder joints, the latter of which
12 likely reflects a small degree of ⁸⁹Zr⁴⁺ dissociation from DFO (**Fig. 3A**) (27). *Ex vivo* biodistribution
13 studies confirmed that both [⁸⁹Zr]Zr-DFO-HM30 and [⁸⁹Zr]Zr-DFO-HM34 remained high in the
14 blood pool at 96 h p.i. (**Fig. 3C**). In parallel, a second cohort of mice was co-injected with an
15 additional 90 μ g of unlabeled HM30 or HM34 alongside 10 μ g of corresponding [⁸⁹Zr]Zr-DFO-
16 HM30/34 to better understand whether accumulation in healthy tissues can be blocked without
17 impacting tumor binding. In both cases, injection with or without co-injection of 90 μ g unlabeled
18 mAb made no difference to liver ($P > 0.99$ and $P = 0.53$) or spleen accumulation 96 h p.i ($P > 0.99$
19 and $P = 0.21$), with [⁸⁹Zr]Zr-DFO-HM30 and [⁸⁹Zr]Zr-DFO-HM34, respectively (**Supplemental Fig.**
20 **7-8**). The estimated effective doses for [⁸⁹Zr]Zr-DFO-HM30 and [⁸⁹Zr]Zr-DFO-HM34, calculated
21 by mouse-to-human extrapolated dosimetry, were comparable, at 0.34 and 0.38 mSv/MBq,
22 respectively. The highest absorbed doses were observed in the liver (1.48 and 1.67 mGy/MBq)
23 and kidneys (1.08 and 1.04 mGy/MBq; **Supplemental Table 1**) for [⁸⁹Zr]Zr-DFO-HM30 and
24 [⁸⁹Zr]Zr-DFO-HM34, respectively.

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 2 **Figure 3. Evaluation of [⁸⁹Zr]Zr-DFO-HM30 and [⁸⁹Zr]Zr-DFO-HM34 in H460 tumor-bearing mice. A.**
 3 Maximum-intensity-projection (MIP, top) and axial slice (bottom) PET/CT images of BALB/c nu/nu mice
 4 bearing subcutaneous H460 tumors at 4, 24, 48, 72 and 96 h p.i. of 10 μg [⁸⁹Zr]Zr-DFO-HM30 or [⁸⁹Zr]Zr-
 5 DFO-HM34. **B.** Tumor image quantification (n = 4). **C.** *Ex vivo* biodistribution with [⁸⁹Zr]Zr-DFO-HM30/34
 6 at 96 h p.i.. Values are expressed as average % ID/g ± SD (n = 4). Comparisons were made by two-way
 7 ANOVA with Bonferroni correction for multiple comparisons.

8
 9 [⁸⁹Zr]Zr-DFO-HM30 immunoPET can distinguish xCT expression *in vivo*

10 To confirm that tumor accumulation was xCT-specific, we next performed imaging with [⁸⁹Zr]Zr-
 11 DFO-HM30 in female mice bearing either H1299 (xCT-low) or H460 (xCT-high) subcutaneous
 12 tumors. As both radioimmunoconjugates performed similarly *in vivo* (**Fig. 3**), [⁸⁹Zr]Zr-DFO-HM30
 13 was taken forward to contextualize our previous study, which used HM30-Tesirine in the same

1 tumor models (15). At 144 h p.i. of [⁸⁹Zr]Zr-DFO-HM30, H460 tumors were clearly visualized by
2 PET/CT imaging, whereas H1299 tumors were not visible above background (**Fig. 4A,**
3 **Supplemental Fig. 9**). The extent of non-specific tumor binding was visualized using a control
4 IgG1 antibody, [⁸⁹Zr]Zr-DFO-hIgG1, in H460 tumor-bearing mice (**Fig. 4A, Supplemental Fig. 9**).
5 Differences in tumor accumulation were quantified by *ex vivo* biodistribution at 144 h, where
6 [⁸⁹Zr]Zr-DFO-HM30 binding was 2.1-fold higher than [⁸⁹Zr]Zr-DFO-hIgG1 (10.83 ± 2.30 and 5.04
7 ± 0.61 % ID/g, respectively, $P < 0.0001$; **Fig. 4B**), confirming specificity for xCT. Similarly, H460
8 (xCT-high) tumors had 2.7-fold higher [⁸⁹Zr]Zr-DFO-HM30 binding than H1299 (xCT-low) tumors
9 (4.05 ± 1.01 % ID/g, $P < 0.0001$; **Fig. 4B**). *Ex vivo* autoradiograms confirmed higher [⁸⁹Zr]Zr-DFO-
10 HM30 accumulation in H460 tumors compared to H1299, corresponding with xCT expression
11 levels (**Supplemental Fig. 10**). There were no differences in [⁸⁹Zr]Zr-DFO-HM30 accumulation in
12 off-target organs, irrespective of the tumor type (**Fig. 4B**). [⁸⁹Zr]Zr-DFO-hIgG1 had reduced
13 accumulation in the lungs compared to [⁸⁹Zr]Zr-DFO-HM30 ($P < 0.0001$), likely due to its faster
14 blood clearance ($P < 0.0001$; **Fig. 4**). In contrast, [⁸⁹Zr]Zr-DFO-hIgG1 signal in the spleen and
15 kidneys was elevated in comparison to [⁸⁹Zr]Zr-DFO-HM30 ($P = 0.0117$ and $P = 0.0007$,
16 respectively; **Fig. 4B**).

1
2 **Figure 4. [⁸⁹Zr]Zr-DFO-HM30 differentiates xCT-high from xCT-low tumors. A.** Representative MIP (top) and axial
3 slice (bottom) PET/CT images of BALB/c nu/nu mice bearing subcutaneous H1299 or H460 tumors at 144 h p.i. of 10
4 μg [⁸⁹Zr]Zr-DFO-HM30 or [⁸⁹Zr]Zr-DFO-hIgG1. **B.** Corresponding *ex vivo* biodistribution from selected tissues. Values
5 are expressed as average % ID/g ± SD (n = 4). Comparisons were made using two-way ANOVA with the Bonferroni
6 correction for multiple comparisons.

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1 [⁸⁹Zr]Zr-DFO-HM30 immunoPET can visualize lung tumors *in vivo*

2 To investigate antibody-based xCT imaging in a more clinically-relevant model, xCT-high H460
3 tumors were grown in the lungs of mice, with [⁸⁹Zr]Zr-DFO-HM30 imaging performed 6 days after
4 inoculation. [⁸⁹Zr]Zr-DFO-HM30 accumulation in H460 lung tumors was significantly higher than
5 healthy lungs (7.81 ± 1.23 vs 4.65 ± 0.34% ID/g, respectively, P < 0.0001; **Fig. 5A, Supplemental**
6 **Fig. 11**). Image analysis revealed a degree of inter-lesion heterogeneity in [⁸⁹Zr]Zr-DFO-HM30
7 binding, both within and between mice (**Fig. 5A, Supplemental Fig. 11**). *Ex vivo* autoradiography
8 and immunohistochemical (IHC) staining of tumor and lung tissue confirmed [⁸⁹Zr]Zr-DFO-HM30
9 accumulation was tumor-specific and corresponded to high xCT expression (**Fig. 5B**).
10 Interestingly, tumored animals had marginally higher accumulation of [⁸⁹Zr]Zr-DFO-HM30 in the
11 heart and spleen compared to healthy animals (P = 0.0331 and P = 0.0390, respectively;
12 **Supplemental Fig. 12**), suggesting prolonged blood circulation in this disease model.

13

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1
 2 **Figure 5. $[^{89}\text{Zr}]\text{Zr-DFO-HM30}$ visualizes xCT-high lung tumors. A.** Representative MIP (top) and
 3 PET/CT images of BALB/c nu/nu mice bearing lung orthotopic H460 tumors or healthy control animals at 144 h p.i. of
 4 $10\ \mu\text{g}$ $[^{89}\text{Zr}]\text{Zr-DFO-HM30}$. Image quantification of $[^{89}\text{Zr}]\text{Zr-DFO-HM30}$ tumor accumulation compared to the lungs of
 5 healthy controls. Values are average \pm SD. Comparisons were made by Welch's t-test. **B.** Representative post-imaging
 6 autoradiogram (ARG), illustrating $[^{89}\text{Zr}]\text{Zr-DFO-HM30}$ accumulation, alongside corresponding H&E- and xCT-stained
 7 tissue sections.

1 Discussion

2 Alterations in tumor redox metabolism bolster antioxidant defences and promote resistance to
3 traditional therapeutics. Central to this mechanism is the cell's predominant antioxidant, GSH,
4 whose increased production is facilitated by upregulated expression of xCT via NRF2 activation.
5 Here, we show that a humanized antibody can noninvasively image xCT expression *in vivo*,
6 visualizing a therapeutically targetable resistance mechanism with immunoPET.

7 Antibody-based therapeutics targeting xCT have shown promise in NSCLC (15), but their *in vivo*
8 behaviour remains poorly characterised. In this study, [⁸⁹Zr]Zr-DFO-HM30 and [⁸⁹Zr]Zr-DFO-
9 HM34 enabled immunoPET visualization of the tumor binding and pharmacokinetics of xCT-
10 directed antibodies. Both tracers exhibited characteristic immunoPET *in vivo* biodistribution,
11 including prolonged blood circulation and accumulation in the liver and spleen, which may reflect
12 the preserved binding affinity of humanized IgGs to murine fragment crystallizable gamma
13 receptors in BALB/c nu/nu mice (28,29). Here, [⁸⁹Zr]Zr-DFO-HM30 demonstrated xCT-specific
14 tumor binding in both subcutaneous and orthotopic NSCLC models, providing an invaluable
15 opportunity to study tumor penetration and off-target accumulation of xCT-targeting therapeutic
16 antibodies.

17 ImmunoPET agents hold great value as diagnostic agents through their high-affinity antigen
18 binding. The antibodies tested here bound xCT with sub-nM K_D and were rapidly internalized.
19 Tumor binding of [⁸⁹Zr]Zr-DFO-HM30, however, did not exceed 11% ID/g at 144 h p.i., despite
20 remaining high in circulation. Interestingly, the level of *in vivo* tumor binding observed with our
21 immunoPET agents matches those reported in a previous immunoPET study targeting LAT1 in
22 colorectal cancer (30). LAT1 and xCT are both membrane-localized by CD98hc, whose bulky
23 ectodomain partially obstructs xCT's small extracellular binding site (26,31), potentially limiting
24 antibody access, thereby reducing contrast. Tumor-to-background ratios could potentially be
25 improved by mapping accessible epitopes to guide the development of next-generation xCT-
26 targeting antibodies. Additionally, targeting xCT with smaller biologics, such as single-domain
27 antibodies or nanobodies, could circumvent potential antigen inaccessibility.

28 Whilst this study describes an xCT immunoPET agent with high xCT affinity and potential as a
29 companion diagnostic, the mAbs' affinity for murine xCT is unknown. Consequently, tumor-to-
30 tissue ratios may be artificially increased as specific accumulation of [⁸⁹Zr]Zr-DFO-HM30 and
31 [⁸⁹Zr]Zr-DFO-HM34 in non-target organs might not be accurately captured. Additionally, xCT is
32 highly expressed on immune cells such as macrophages (32). To visualize interactions with these

1 immune cells, more complex mouse models, such as mice with humanized immune systems
2 (33,34), should be used in future studies.

3 Theranostics are set to redefine the cancer treatment paradigm. High affinity, specificity, and
4 versatile conjugation methods have made antibodies a popular choice as theranostic agents. In
5 addition to radionuclide therapy approaches, combination strategies with a PET-compatible
6 radioimmunoconjugate for diagnosis and an ADC for therapy hold great promise. We have
7 previously demonstrated the capability of the xCT-targeting ADC, HM30-tesirine, to halt tumor
8 growth in xCT-high H460 tumors, whilst growth was unaffected in xCT-low H1299 xenografts (15).
9 Our data establishes [⁸⁹Zr]Zr-DFO-HM30 as a companion imaging agent for xCT-directed
10 therapeutics such as HM30-tesirine, providing insight into the tumor penetration of these antibody-
11 based agents. [⁸⁹Zr]Zr-DFO-HM30 immunoPET provides a foundation to develop more effective
12 ADCs and a framework for exploring targeted radionuclide therapy using xCT-directed antibodies.
13 Clinically, these strategies are particularly compelling in NRF2/KEAP1-altered NSCLC, where
14 xCT upregulation drives therapy resistance and underscores the need for targeted interventions.
15 Together, these findings position xCT immunoPET as both an effective imaging tool for drug
16 development and a gateway to theranostic applications in redox-rewired cancers.

17

18 **Conclusion**

19 In summary, we have developed an antibody-based radioligand targeting human xCT,
20 demonstrating specific binding in preclinical models of NSCLC and excellent tumor visualization
21 by PET. This imaging agent provides a direct window into the *in vivo* biodistribution and tumor
22 binding of xCT-directed ADC therapies that could revolutionize the treatment of NSCLC.

23

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1 **KEY POINTS**

2 **QUESTION:** Can antibody-based PET imaging agents visualize xCT expression and image the
3 *in vivo* biodistribution of their therapeutic counterparts in preclinical models of NSCLC?

4 **PERTINENT FINDINGS:** [⁸⁹Zr]Zr-DFO-HM30 is an effective imaging tool to visualize tumor
5 penetration, target binding, and pharmacokinetics of antibody-based xCT-directed therapeutics in
6 NSCLC.

7 **IMPLICATIONS FOR PATIENT CARE:** xCT immunoPET enables evaluation of next-generation
8 chemo- and radiotherapeutic strategies incorporating antibodies to target xCT-upregulation in
9 NRF2/KEAP1-altered NSCLC.

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